

Nicola Scaldaferrì and Steven Feld (eds.), *When the Trees Resound. Collaborative Media Research on an Italian Festival*, english edition edited with an introduction by Lorenzo Ferrarini, photographs by Stefano Vaja and Lorenzo Ferrarini, Udine, Nota, 150 pp, with 2 CDs, 2019. ISBN 9788861631557.

In the wooded areas of the regions of Basilicata and Calabria in southern Italy, trees are protagonists of remarkable festivals which have long been the object of anthropological research. Following a rich religious calendar focused on the devotion of specific Catholic saints, these events take place annually in several small villages of the regions, and involve complex rituals of great sonic and choreographic intensity. Long described as surviving manifestations of ancient pagan fertility cults in the form of popular religiosity, these festivals demand to be fully understood in their current expression. This task compels scholars to go beyond traditional theoretical frameworks, which have always privileged the study of the symbolic and historical dimensions, in order to shed light also on the importance of the peculiar sensory, affective, and performative components that are at the core of the participants' experience and that may orient us toward more emphatic research trajectories.

Nicola Scaldaferrì, an Italian ethnomusicologist and expert in Basilicata's musical practices, bore this imperative in mind when he decided to assemble an interdisciplinary team in May 2005 to conduct collaborative ethnographic research on one of the most famous tree festivals in Basilicata: the Festival of Saint Julian in the village of Accettura, also known locally as the *Maggio*. In collaboration with the American sound anthropologist Steven Feld, and the photographers Stefano Vaja and Lorenzo Ferrarini, Scaldaferrì coordinated a four-day immersive inquiry into the musical and sonic practices of the *Maggio*, the innovative results of which appeared in the form of a multimedia and multi-authorial book in 2012, titled *I suoni dell'Albero*. Originally published in Italian, the book is now available to an international audience thanks to the recent release of its new English edition, retitled *When the Trees Resound*.¹

Producing an English version of the text does present certain immediate challenges such as the difficulty in translating the crucial concept *festa arborea*. Although rendered as "tree festival", the original Italian carries additional connotative significance not captured by the English, and is frequently associated with such terms as "vegetative ritual" and "arboreal cult" in the Anglophone context. Still, *When the Trees Resound* offers a remarkable study to the English-speaking world both for its subject matter and its methodology, combining photography, text, and audio to provide an evocative portrait of the aural universe of the *Maggio* festival. Through its methodological innovations, the book

¹ Digital version available at: <<http://leavlab.com/portfolio/when-the-trees-resound-2019/>>

asserts the centrality of sound and music in the festival, as both organizing principles and participatory tools. While the aural components have been long neglected from previous scholarly accounts which were centered on textual and disembodied renditions of the *Maggio*, stemming from analyses based on evolutionary and interpretative models, Scaldaferrri and his team demonstrate that the dense and apparently chaotic layering of sounds is crucial to the unfolding of the festival, which comprises a number of phases. To summarize very briefly: two trees are cut and transported into the center of the village; joined together, they become a new entity (the *Maggio*), which is decorated, erected and climbed by youths.

These ritualized actions involve complex sensory experiences through and in sound, calling for a rethinking of the criteria of ethnographic representation and documentation. In this regard, the book enters into dialogue with the latest debates in the fields of sensory anthropology and ethnomusicology, revolving around an experimental use of recording technologies placed at the intersection between artistic and research practices and informed by deep phenomenological and dialogic approaches. These themes have always been at the core of the research trajectories of the book's curators, Nicola Scaldaferrri and Steven Feld, whose collaboration dates back to a previous project in Basilicata about carnival bells.²

In *When the Trees Resound*, Scaldaferrri's in-depth knowledge of the *Maggio* in Accettura as both a native researcher of the area and active *zampogna* [bagpipe] player, along with his strong commitment to audiovisual and collaborative research methods, enables him to enter into a fruitful conversation with Feld's most influential theoretical and methodological contributions, deriving from his long-standing fieldwork experience in Papua New Guinea.³ Beyond sharing similar research interests, the authors are united by a common formation in electro-acoustic composition and an analogous mode of inquiry revolving around their activity as researcher-performers. While both aspects emerge in the book at different moments and according to different modalities, the former provides a significant key to reading the work as a whole.

As the team photographer Ferrarini remarks in his addended opening text to the English edition, which introduces the work to a more international audience, the book and its audiovisual components are based on a polyphonic principle. With the assemblage of short essays and the inclusion of two photographic series and two CDs, multiple partial views and objects come together to render the sonic complexity of the festive event and to produce an evocative effect for the reader unaware of it. In opposition to standard ethnographies which rely on the written text to convey their knowledge, in *When the Trees Resound*, the narration of the phenomenon occurs primarily through sound and

² Nicola Scaldaferrri, *Santi, animali e suoni. Feste dei campanacci a Tricarico e San Mauro Forte*, with photographs by Stefano Vaja and CD by Steven Feld, Udine, Nota, 2005.

³ Steven Feld, *Sound and Sentiment: Birds, Weeping, Poetics and Song in Kaluli Expression*, Durham, Duke University Press, 2012 (1st ed. 1982).

image and the juxtapositions between them. The suggestive representation of the dense emotive and sensory universe of the festival which ultimately emerges is emphasized through the skillful employment of artistic and compositional techniques in the arrangement and conception of each contribution.

While Vaja's photographic series focuses on the recurrence of ancient gestures in the festival through the contrast of black and white photographs, Ferrarini's stresses specific visual elements – trees, bagpipes, ropes, tools – and their rhythmicity in the frames. The still images of the latter photographer overlap with many moments rich in sound that feature in the six tracks of Feld's soundscape composition in CD1, which might be viewed simultaneously as an analysis, synthesis and poetic re-elaboration of the sound memory of the researcher's body moving in the ritual. The US anthropologist's well-established and favorite research medium, i.e. the soundscape composition, contrasts with the more traditional documentation by Scaldaferrri in CD2. In the latter audio compilation, the overview of the musical repertoire of the village of Accettura combines sound documents from the ethnomusicologist's personal archive, from the 2005 festival, alongside the impressive collection of recordings by Accettura's resident priest, Giuseppe Filardi (also author of a valuable essay in the book, concerning the local history of the ritual). The plurality of views, which includes the different authors' textual contributions, undermines any notion of ethnographic authority and grants the reader a certain autonomy in terms of the way he might choose to read, view, and listen to the work.

While pursuing contrasting approaches to acoustic documentation, the CDs are especially conceived as complementary to each other, as the editors explain in detail in the dialogue at the center of the book. This section devotes major attention to discussing the research strategies and compositional criteria behind the soundscape approach. The adoption of sophisticated microphones to be worn on his head allows Feld to evoke the perspective of a mobile listener who participates in the *Maggio* and moves with the body through the dense stratification of human, mechanical, and natural sounds accompanying each phase of the ritual. Specific montage operations heighten the evocative effect of the recordings, challenging the boundaries between documentation and evocation, research and artistic practice. Instead of dissecting the numerous formal and improvisational musical performances that happen during the festival from their context, the characteristic *zampogna* songs are heard among the sounds of oxen, cowbells, sermons, cries and firecrackers, resulting in a deeply phenomenological portrayal of the ritual's unfolding through time and space. What also emerges from this conversation, among other relevant issues, is the ethical stance that Feld attributes to the soundscape approach and which traces back to his early formulations on “dialogic editing”. Beyond listening critically to the phenomenon under investigation and editing carefully, it is equally important to bring the work back to the local community for their criticism and feedback.

In response to this, the new edition in English integrates three interviews with protagonists of the festival, which expand the polyphonic account in a more explicitly dia-

logic direction. In the section “Back in the Field”, local inhabitants of Accettura reveal their perspectives of the ritual and, moreover, share their impressions of the book two years after its publication in Italian. Feld’s original purposes with respect to the soundscape composition are matched by the inhabitants’ comments which invoke the power of the piece to make them relive the ritual sonically, while also acknowledging its highly-edited nature. With the incorporation of the voices of local participants, which reinforce the masculine view of the festival (a topic that might have benefitted from further inquiry in the text), experiential meanings once again emerge stronger than ancestral or symbolic ones, confirming the hypothesis that the anthropologist Fernando Mirizzi hints at in his essay on the history of scholarly writing of the *Maggio*.

Mirizzi illustrates the way in which anthropological literature has ended up shaping popular perceptions of the event, shifted from a socio-religious event to an instance of cultural heritage. In this context, it might be worth reflecting once again upon the way in which *When the Trees Resound* could potentially affect the community approach to the ritual in the long-term, beyond the precious comments gathered in the book. In an epoch of social distancing in which festivals and rituals all over the world have been canceled or subject to strong limitations, what role might audiovisual research aimed at dialogic and embodied representations play for local communities? How might the audiovisual components of the book interact with and acquire a new meaning in light of the massive media coverage of the phenomenon?

Overall, *When the Trees Resound* is an ambitious project that relies not only on scholarly rigor, but on highly specialized technical and artistic skills. Because of its scope, and because it does not fit within the traditional format of academic publishing, it might be difficult to replicate this project in other contexts. But that only enhances its merit and its daring. In particular, moreover, the work suggests new methodological trajectories for future research in ethnomusicology and anthropology, productively pushing the fields towards an increasingly more collaborative and creative scholarship.

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